

Electronic structure and stability of the active surface phase of $\text{Ni}_x\text{Co}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ spinel alkaline O_2 evolution electrocatalysts: from an epitaxial model catalyst perspective

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Abstract

In this work, we investigate the relationship between the surface stability, electronic structure of Ni^{3+} hole states and oxygen evolution reaction (OER) activity in epitaxially grown $\text{Ni}_x\text{Co}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ ($x = 0, 0.3, 1.0$) model electrocatalysts through analysis of their electronic structure before and after electrochemical treatments. The use of flat, structurally well-defined models allows to apply advanced characterization methods, not applicable to powder catalysts. The OER activity of all $\text{Ni}_x\text{Co}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ samples increases consistently upon cyclic voltammetry (CV) between +1.22 V and +1.92 V vs.

RHE with proceeding cycles. Quasi in-situ synchrotron X-ray photoemission spectroscopy (SXPS) results show a gradual up-shift of the Fermi level (E_F) for all $\text{Ni}_x\text{Co}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ after progressing OER electrochemical treatment, while near edge X-ray absorption fine structure spectroscopy (NEXAFS) of the O K-edge, as well as the Co and Ni L-edges show no significant changes in the hole state structure near the conduction band minimum as well as the oxidation state of Ni and Co upon OER treatment. A combination of atomic force microscopy, spectroscopic ellipsometry, X-ray diffraction and X-ray reflectivity measurements reveals that the surface of $\text{Ni}_x\text{Co}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ reconstructs and builds up oxygen deficiency upon OER treatment. While the upshift of the Fermi level is disadvantageous for the OER, the emerging oxygen deficiency together with morphology changes lead to an overall increase of OER activity.

Keywords: Ni-doped Co_3O_4 , oxygen evolution reaction, single crystal, electronic structure, hole state

Introduction

Electrochemical water splitting provides a promising pathway to store renewable (solar, wind) energy in chemical bonds and will be a key component for the transition to a CO_2 -neutral future energy system.^{1,2} The oxygen evolution reaction (OER) limits the efficiency of water electrolysis due to the higher overpotential caused by the four electron/proton transfer process during OER.³ Therefore, the development of efficient, stable and low-cost OER electrocatalysts is critical to the practical implementation of water electrolysis.⁴ Although the current commercial IrO_2 - and RuO_2 -based catalysts for acidic water electrolysis have excellent OER activity, their scarcity and instability hinder the large-scale application of PEM electrolysis.^{5,6} Therefore, cheap, earth-abundant and stable transition metal oxides are becoming more attractive, especially Fe, Co and Ni, when alkaline water electrolysis is considered.⁷⁻⁹ Among them, the spinel AB_2O_4 oxides have attracted great attention due to their high activity and tunable electronic structure properties through, e.g., doping.^{10,11} Recently, in several spinel oxides, surface reconstruction during OER has been observed, and the reconstructed surface is usually considered as the active phase defining the atomic and electronic structure of the electrode-electrolyte interface.^{12,13} Thus, it is critical to investigate the physicochemical properties of the reconstructed surface under operando conditions, yielding insight into the design basis for optimally performing metal oxide semiconductor OER electrocatalysts.^{14,15} Previous reports have shown that Co-based

spinel oxides readily convert to higher oxidation states of Co hydroxides or amorphous layers during the OER process.^{16,17} For instance, Duan et al. combined experimental results and theoretical calculations, by which they demonstrated that Ni doping of ZnCo_2O_4 would activate lattice oxygen to participate in the OER reaction, resulting in surface reconstruction to form a catalytically highly active oxyhydroxide species.¹⁸ In another study, it was demonstrated by Raman spectroscopy that the active phase of mesoporous NiCo_2O_4 nanosheets is the spinel phase itself, however iron doping facilitated the transformation of this spinel phase into electrocatalytically more active $\text{Ni}(\text{Co})$ oxyhydroxide species.¹⁹ Recently, Reikowski et al. reported operando surface X-ray diffraction data suggesting that the surface of Co_3O_4 undergoes surface reconstruction during OER progress, leading to the formation of CoOOH layers, being described as the active surface phase.²⁰

Co_3O_4 , a typical spinel oxide, has been widely studied due to its high OER activity and good stability in alkaline electrolytes.²¹ A number of strategies have been explored to improve its OER activity including nanostructure engineering to increase the surface area,^{22,23} exposing more active crystal facets,²⁴ and aliovalent doping to increase the electrical conductivity and to modulate electronic structure.^{25,26} Aliovalent doping is a powerful method to enhance the OER performance of Co_3O_4 , especially when using nickel. Li et al. have reported that Ni-doped Co_3O_4 led to an increase in electrical conductivity along with the formation of Ni^{3+} , which contributed to the enhancement of its OER activity.²⁷ Moreover, in our recent study, we found that doping by Ni can significantly improve the OER performance of Co_3O_4 .²⁸ However, the modulation of the electronic structure of Co_3O_4 by doping with Ni was found as the key factor to the improvement of its OER activity, rather than an increase in bulk electrical conductivity. We argue that filled electronic states near the Fermi level E_F improve the orbital overlap with key OER reaction intermediates, favoring their formation. At the same time, unoccupied states close above the E_F increase the electron affinity of the oxide semiconductors, thereby facilitating charge transfer at the interface associated with water oxidation. To date, most previous works have been based on the nanostructures to investigate the OER performance of Ni-doped Co_3O_4 . However, there has been limited work to investigate the electronic structure as well as the OER properties of Ni-doped Co_3O_4 using flat, structurally well-defined model systems, which enable more in-depth structure, morphology, and electronic structure analyses. Although we have established the conformational relationship between the electronic structure of Ni-doped Co_3O_4 and its catalytic properties,²⁸ the stability of the chemical, surface, and electronic structures as the OER progresses still needs to be investigated and verified. Therefore, establishing a clear relationship between the surface properties (i.e., active

surface phase composition, atomic and electronic structure) and the OER activity of Ni-doped Co_3O_4 using single-crystal thin films as a catalytic model is essential for the design of more efficient and stable catalysts.

In this work, we used pulsed laser deposition (PLD) to grow $\text{Ni}_x\text{Co}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ ($x = 0, 0.3, 1.0$) single crystalline thin films on conducting 0.1% Nb-doped SrTiO_3 (001) substrates. The relationship between the surface properties, electronic structure and OER activity after different cyclic voltammetry (CV) treatments was investigated by a combination of atomic force microscope (AFM), spectroscopic ellipsometry, synchrotron X-ray photoemission spectroscopy (SXPS) and near-edge X-ray absorption fine structure (NEXAFS). Our results show that the surface of the $\text{Ni}_x\text{Co}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ thin films undergoes morphology change during CV treatment, resulting in the E_F of these materials to gradually shift upward with increasing CV cycles. The upward shift of E_F indicates an increase in the distance between the O p-band center (that is the valance band maximum) and E_F , resulting in a decrease in the orbital overlap with oxygen intermediate and thus weaker bond strength, which, in turn, is unfavorable for OER performance. In addition, the electronic structure was evaluated to be rather stable with OER cycling, as inferred from the oxidation states of Co and Ni as well as the hole state below the conduction band minimum (CBM). Furthermore, there are three effects on the OER performance of $\text{Ni}_x\text{Co}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$, including E_F upshift, morphology change and oxygen deficiency. Most importantly, the underlying results demonstrate that the OER activity of $\text{Ni}_x\text{Co}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ exhibits a strong correlation with the appearance of oxygen deficiency and change of Ni/Co ratio at the sample surface being the predominant control parameter for overall OER activity.

Experimental section

Materials preparation

$\text{Ni}_x\text{Co}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ ($x = 0, 0.3, 1.0$) targets were synthesized by solid-phase reaction. Stoichiometric amounts of NiO (Alfa, > 99.999%) and Co_3O_4 (Alfa, > 99.999%) were mixed in a mortar. After grinding for 2 hours, the powder was pressed into pellets through a hydraulic press at 10 tons of pressure for 2 minutes, and finally these pellets were calcined in a muffle furnace (Kejing, KSL-1700) at 1000 °C for 24 h with a 5 °C/min heating rate. $\text{Ni}_x\text{Co}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ ($x = 0, 0.3, 1.0$) single crystalline thin films were grown on one-side polished (100)-oriented 0.1% Nb-doped SrTiO_3 (HeFei, Kejing) substrates by PLD using the respective oxide targets. Laser ablation was performed at

a repetition rate of 5 Hz and an energy density of 1.0 J/cm² with a 248 nm KrF excimer laser. To achieve ~40 nm film thicknesses, the laser was impinged on the target for 15 min applying a substrate temperature of 550 °C and an O₂ partial pressure of 30 mTorr.

Materials characterization

The crystal structure of the pure Ni_xCo_{3-x}O₄ (x = 0, 0.3, 1.0) targets was analyzed by X-ray diffraction (XRD) using Cu K α radiation generated at 40 kV and 44 mA. Thin film growth was examined by high-resolution X-ray diffraction using a rotating Cu anode (45 kV, 190 mA) Rigaku SmartLab diffractometer in θ -2 θ geometry, equipped with a Ge (220) double bounce monochromator (selecting the Cu K α ₁ wavelength) in parallel beam mode, while the thickness of the films was determined by X-ray reflectivity (XRR) scans on the SmartLab. The surface morphology of the Ni_xCo_{3-x}O₄ sample before and after OER treatments were determined by atomic force microscopy (AFM) with Bruker Icon Dimension AFM in amplitude modulation mode using PPP-Zeihl cantilevers (NanoAndMore GmbH, Wetzlar, Germany). The scanning area of sample surface was 1 x 1 μ m² or 1.5 x 1.5 μ m² applying a tip velocity of 2 μ m/s.

The SXPS and NEXAFS measurements were performed at the soft X-ray spectroscopy undulator beamline U49-2_PGM-1 at BESSY II synchrotron in Berlin, which provides photons in the energy range of 85 – 1600 eV. The Solid-Liquid-Interface Analysis System (SOLIAS) endstation has been used and spectra were measured at normal emissions using a Phoibos 150 (SPECS) energy analyzer with 1D delay line detector.²⁹ An Ar ion sputter-cleaned Au foil served as a calibration sample by making use of the Au 4f_{7/2} transition located at 84.0 eV.³⁰ Excitation energies were adjusted for each core level to measure the photoelectrons at a similar kinetic energy of 550 eV (or 500 eV for the valence band edge), leading to an investigation of each element in a similar depth of analysis, *i.e.*, three times the inelastic mean free path at 550 eV (1.2–1.3 nm).³¹ The spectra of ellipsometric angles ψ and Δ as well as the depolarization have been recorded by a dual rotating compensator ellipsometer in the isotropic mode between 190 nm and 2500 nm at angles of incidence of 50°, 60° and 70°. We analyzed the data using transfer-matrix calculus assuming a four-phase layer model including semi-infinite substrate, the materials layer, and a surface roughness layer bounded by air. The dielectric function (DF) of the SrTiO₃ substrate was obtained from modeling ellipsometry data taken from a pure substrate using a b-spline approach.^{32,33} The layers DF we also modeled with a b-spline approach and that of the roughness layer by a Bruggeman effective medium approximation (EMA) mixing the DF of the material and air equally

assuming a depolarization factor of 0.333.³⁴

Electrochemical measurements were carried out in a three-electrode configuration using a Palmsens (Palmsens BV, Netherlands) electrochemical workstation setup in the double cross glass electrochemistry chamber of the SOLIAS endstation.²⁹ Such a set-up gives the opportunity to perform SXPS and NEXAFS without atmosphere exposure between the measurements and the electrochemical treatments. A platinum wire was used as a counter electrode and Hg/HgO (1 M KOH) as a reference electrode. Cyclic voltammetry (CV) measurements were performed under inert, dry, carbon-free argon atmosphere in 1 M KOH at a scan rate of 10 mV/s with the potential from +1.22 to +1.92 V (*vs.* RHE). Each sample was subjected to four OER treatments, namely 0 CV (exposure to electrolyte only), 3 CV (+3), 10 CV (+7), and 30 CV (+20) cycles. After each treatment step, the sample was rinsed with MilliQ water and blown dry by Ar, then transferred to the vacuum system of the SOLIAS endstation for spectroscopic investigation.

Structural characterization of pristine and tested samples by XRD and XRR

XRD and XRR were employed to characterize the structural properties of $\text{Ni}_x\text{Co}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ thin films grown on Nb-doped SrTiO_3 (001) substrates by PLD. The total thickness (including crystalline and amorphous layer) of the sample can be detected by XRR. Figure 1a shows the XRD results of pristine Co_3O_4 thin films (black curve) and after 30 CV cycles (i.e., after all four treatment steps, red curve), the peak at $2\theta = 46.4^\circ$ corresponds to the (002) orientation of the Nb-doped SrTiO_3 single crystal substrate, while the peak at 44.8° can be indexed as the (004)- reflection of spinel Co_3O_4 . As shown in the Figure 1b and 1c, the peaks at 44.6° and 44.2° correspond to the (004) orientation in $\text{Ni}_{0.3}\text{Co}_2\text{O}_4$ and NiCo_2O_4 , respectively. There is gradual shift of XRD peak position to lower angles with increasing Ni doping concentration (Figure S1), due to the substitution of Co by Ni possessing a larger atomic radius leading to expansion of the lattice parameters. To determine the thickness of the Co_3O_4 thin film, we measured and fitted the obtained XRR data. As shown in Figure S2, the thickness of the $\text{Ni}_x\text{Co}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ ($x = 0, 0.3, 1.0$) single crystal thin film is 40 ± 0.2 nm. After 30 CV cycles between +1.22 V to +1.92 V (*vs.* RHE) in 1 M KOH, the distance between the Kiessig fringes (Figure 1d) did not change significantly, which means that the overall thickness of the Co_3O_4 film remains unchanged. However, the peak intensity of the (004)-peak of the Co_3O_4 film decreased after 30 CV cycles, allowing the assumption that electrochemical treatment leads to a deterioration of film crystallinity not only at the surface, but also in the bulk structure (since XRD provides information of both owing to the penetration

depth of the X-rays). The weakening of the XRD diffraction peak intensity after OER treatment is attributed to the morphology change of the Co_3O_4 surface and bulk structure with OER cycling, a phenomenon which has been observed for Co_3O_4 in numerous previous reports.^{20,35} For $\text{Ni}_{0.3}\text{Co}_{2.7}\text{O}_4$, peak intensity remained constant after 30 CV cycles but the thickness of the film increased slightly to 41 ± 0.1 nm (Figure S1e). In addition, the diffraction peak position of NiCo_2O_4 in Figure 1c shifts from 44.28° to 44.20° after 30 CV cycles, which indicates that the lattice constant of the thin film increased from 8.173 \AA ($a = b = c = 8.173 \text{ \AA}$) to 8.187 \AA ($a = b = c = 8.187 \text{ \AA}$) during the OER process.

Figure 1. XRD and XRR of $\text{Ni}_x\text{Co}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ thin films in pristine state (black curves) and after 30 CV cycles (red curves). (a) XRD of Co_3O_4 , (b) XRD of $\text{Ni}_{0.3}\text{Co}_{2.7}\text{O}_4$, (c) XRD of NiCo_2O_4 , (d) XRR of Co_3O_4 , (e) XRR of $\text{Ni}_{0.3}\text{Co}_{2.7}\text{O}_4$ and (f) XRR of NiCo_2O_4 .

Surface morphology assessed by AFM

To investigate the effect of electrochemical treatments on the surface morphology of the different thin films, we carried out AFM measurements for $\text{Ni}_x\text{Co}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ ($x = 0, 0.3, 1.0$) in pristine state (as-prepared) and after 30 CV cycles. As shown in Figure 2a, pristine Co_3O_4 possesses a flat surface with a root mean square roughness (RMS) of 0.7 nm, while the RMS increased to 1.0 nm after 30 CV cycles (Figure 2b). The slightly larger RMS of Co_3O_4 after 30 CV cycles can be most likely ascribed to morphology change of Co_3O_4 thin film with OER cycling and is in good accordance with the XRD and XPS data (see Figure 1 and Figure 4). The AFM images of $\text{Ni}_{0.3}\text{Co}_{2.7}\text{O}_4$ thin films

before and after OER treatment are shown in Figures 2c and 2d, presenting that the RMS increased from 0.8 nm to 1.3 nm after 30 CV cycles. However, NiCo_2O_4 films showed a significant reduction in RMS after 30 CV cycles (Figures 2e and 2f), from 1.0 nm to 0.4 nm. The influence of OER treatment on the surface properties of $\text{Ni}_x\text{Co}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ films can be further observed in the corresponding AFM 3D images in Figure S3. Among them, the changes in the NiCo_2O_4 film due to OER treatment were most pronounced. Overall, the morphology changes with OER cycling leads to a change in the roughness and particle size of all $\text{Ni}_x\text{Co}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ thin films.

Figure 2. AFM of $\text{Ni}_x\text{Co}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ thin films in pristine state and after 30 CV cycles. (a)

Co₃O₄ pristine, (b) Co₃O₄ after 30 CV, (c) Ni_{0.3}Co_{2.7}O₄ pristine, (d) Ni_{0.3}Co_{2.7}O₄ after 30 CV, (e) NiCo₂O₄ pristine and (f) NiCo₂O₄ after 30 CV.

Spectroscopic ellipsometry

To further investigate the thickness and roughness of all Ni_xCo_{3-x}O₄ thin films, we employed spectroscopic ellipsometry. The results are shown in Figure 3 and Figure S4. For obtaining the materials dielectric function (DF) as well as the thickness of the main layer and the surface roughness, we applied a so-called multi-sample fitting approach to reduce parameter correlations, forcing materials DF, Bruggeman effective medium approximation (EMA) properties, and thickness of the main layer to be the same for the pristine and CV-treated (see XRR results) samples, only allowing the thickness of the surface roughness layer to differ for both in the Levenberg-Marquard fitting algorithm. The thickness and roughness values of all samples, i.e., pristine and after 30 CV cycles per composition, are summarized in Table 1. The thickness values of all Ni_xCo_{3-x}O₄ thin films before and after OER treatments are around 40 nm, which is in good agreement with XRR results. In addition, it can be observed that the surface roughness of both Co₃O₄ and Ni_{0.3}Co_{2.7}O₄ films shows an increasing trend after 30 CV cycles, while the opposite trend was observed for NiCo₂O₄ films. The change in the surface roughness for all Ni_xCo_{3-x}O₄ follows the same trend with AFM results and XRR fitting results (Table S1), but the absolute values are not identical.

Figure 3. Experimental (dashed lines) and modeled (solid lines) spectroscopic ellipsometry data in terms of the pseudo-dielectric function $\langle \epsilon \rangle = \langle \epsilon_1 \rangle + i\langle \epsilon_2 \rangle$ for Co₃O₄. (a) pristine sample and (b) sample after 30 CV cycles.

Table 1. Spectroscopic ellipsometry-derived thickness and roughness values of $\text{Ni}_x\text{Co}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ ($x = 0, 0.3, 1.0$) at pristine state and after 30 CV cycles.

Sample	Thickness (nm)	Roughness (nm)
Co_3O_4 pristine	36.0 ± 0.1	1.12 ± 0.16
Co_3O_4 after 30 CV	36.6 ± 0.1	4.05 ± 0.02
$\text{Ni}_{0.3}\text{Co}_{2.7}\text{O}_4$ pristine	42.1 ± 0.2	0.72 ± 0.22
$\text{Ni}_{0.3}\text{Co}_{2.7}\text{O}_4$ after 30 CV	42.8 ± 0.3	1.20 ± 0.26
NiCo_2O_4 pristine	40.0 ± 0.4	3.20 ± 0.02
NiCo_2O_4 after 30 CV	40.2 ± 0.4	1.17 ± 0.02

Electronic structure by X-ray photoemission and absorption spectroscopies

The stability of the chemical surface and electronic structure of $\text{Ni}_x\text{Co}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ ($x = 0, 0.3, 1.0$) after OER treatment was investigated by SXPS and NEXAFS. Figure 4a shows Co 2p core level spectra of Co_3O_4 after different OER treatments, the spin-orbit doublets located at 779.3 eV and 794.5 eV corresponding to Co 2p_{3/2} and 2p_{1/2}, and the satellite peak at 785-790 eV indicate the presence of mixed Co^{2+} and Co^{3+} oxidation states in Co_3O_4 .³⁶ The Co 2p spectra do not change significantly after different OER treatments, but the peak position gradually shifts to higher binding energy (BE) with increasing number of CV cycles. The same shift is also seen in the corresponding O 1s core level spectra (Figure 4b). Also, the SXPS valence band spectra of Co_3O_4 (Figure 4c) as well as the distance of valence band maximum (VBM) to E_F increased by the same amount with increasing number of CV cycles, indicating an upward movement of E_F or alternatively a downward movement of the VBM. By combining the systematic shift of the BE of both Co 2p and O 1s core levels as well as the shift of the VB spectrum (Figure 4d), we can finally clarify the upward shift of E_F with CV cycling. The upward shift of E_F is attributed to the morphology change of Co_3O_4 during OER treatment, which is consistent with the structural results derived by XRD, XRR, and AFM. In addition, the SXPS data of $\text{Ni}_{0.3}\text{Co}_{2.7}\text{O}_4$ and NiCo_2O_4 with different numbers of CV cycles are shown in Figures S5 and S6, respectively, consolidating the systematic shift of the core level (Co 2p and O 1s) and VB spectra as observed in Co_3O_4 . These findings indicate that with progressing OER treatment a gradual energetic upshift of E_F is

occurring for all investigated samples.

Figure 4. Co₃O₄ SXPS of (a) Co 2p, (b) O 1s, (c) VB spectra with different CV cycles and (d) shifts of core-level binding energy and Fermi level (E_F) position relative to the VBM deduced from the change of Co 2p, O 1s and VBM BE as a function of CV cycles.

To further investigate the Co oxidation states of Co₃O₄ after different CV cycles, the Co L-edge NEXAFS is shown in Figure S7a. The Co L-edge spin-orbit splitting results in L₃ and L₂ peaks located at 780.4 eV and 794.8 eV along with the shoulders at around 778 eV and 796 eV indicating the presence of Co²⁺ and Co³⁺ in Co₃O₄, which agrees well with the data reported in the literature.³⁷ With increasing number of CV cycles, the L₃ and L₂ edges changed slightly, which indicates that the ratio of Co²⁺ and Co³⁺ qualitatively changed during the OER process; the changes do not increase gradually with the CV cycle. Similarly, the ratio of Co²⁺ and Co³⁺ changed slightly in Ni_{0.3}Co_{2.7}O₄ and NiCo₂O₄ with OER treatment as shown in Figure 5c and Figure 5d, respectively. Meanwhile, the NEXAFS spectra of the Ni L-edge shown in Figure 5e and 5f correspond to Ni_{0.3}Co_{2.7}O₄ and NiCo₂O₄, the L₃ and L₂ of Ni L-edge stay virtually unaltered with increasing number of CV cycles, which indicates that the oxidation state of Ni remains stable. The trend seen in the Co L-edge spectra relates well with the shift of the SXPS Co 2p and O 1s core levels as function of number of CV cycles being due to an upward shift of E_F rather than to a change in Co oxidation state. The O K-edge

NEXAS was used to probe the unoccupied states above E_F near the conduction band minimum,³⁴ the O K-edge results of Co_3O_4 , $\text{Ni}_{0.3}\text{Co}_{2.7}\text{O}_4$ and NiCo_2O_4 are shown in Figure S7b, Figure 5a and Figure 5b, respectively. For Co_3O_4 , the single peak at 530.7 eV corresponds to hybridization of unoccupied Co 3d and O 2p orbitals, it shows negligible change with increasing CV cycles. For pristine $\text{Ni}_{0.3}\text{Co}_{2.7}\text{O}_4$ and NiCo_2O_4 , there is a new hole state (seen as a shoulder at around 529 eV) emerging, which is associated with the emptied e_g orbitals of Ni^{3+} .³⁸ To investigate the stability of this hole state as function of increasing number of CV cycles, we compared the intensity of the hole state at 530.7 eV (Figure 5a and 5b) with progressing OER treatment, as shown in Figure S8. The results show that this hole state in $\text{Ni}_{0.3}\text{Co}_{2.7}\text{O}_4$ and NiCo_2O_4 is rather stable and stays unaffected by OER treatment. Since this hole state is derived from Ni^{3+} , the stability of this hole state further confirms that the oxidation state of Ni does not change with increasing number of CV cycles, which agrees well with the Ni L-edge results.

Figure 5. NEXAFS spectra of $\text{Ni}_{0.3}\text{Co}_{2.7}\text{O}_4$ and NiCo_2O_4 corresponding to different CV cycles. (a) O K-edge of $\text{Ni}_{0.3}\text{Co}_{2.7}\text{O}_4$, (b) O K-edge of NiCo_2O_4 , (c) Co L-edge of $\text{Ni}_{0.3}\text{Co}_{2.7}\text{O}_4$, (d) Co L-edge of NiCo_2O_4 , (e) Ni L-edge of $\text{Ni}_{0.3}\text{Co}_{2.7}\text{O}_4$, (f) Ni L-edge of NiCo_2O_4 . The concentration of the hole state was quantified by the peak areas of the O K-edge features at 529 and 530 eV.

Electrochemical results

The OER performance of $\text{Ni}_x\text{Co}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ ($x = 0, 0.3, 1.0$) thin films with different CV cycles were evaluated in a standard three-electrode setup in a double-cross glass electrochemistry cell of the SOLIAS endstation in 1 M KOH solution recorded with a 10 mV/s scan rate for a potential range of +1.22 V to +1.92 V vs. RHE. Figure 6a shows the different CV cycles of NiCo_2O_4 with current density normalized by the geometrical

area of the thin film without ohmic compensation.³⁹ The corresponding CV curves of Co_3O_4 and $\text{Ni}_{0.3}\text{Co}_{2.7}\text{O}_4$ are shown in Figure S9. The results suggest that the OER activity of NiCo_2O_4 experiences a significant enhancement with increasing number of CV cycles, pointing at an initial formation of an active surface phase, i.e., activation of the catalyst. To compare the OER activity of $\text{Ni}_x\text{Co}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ with different Ni doping concentrations, the current densities of these samples for proceeding CV cycles at +1.8 V (vs. RHE) are illustrated in Figure 6b. The data show that the initial OER performance of $\text{Ni}_x\text{Co}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ is enhanced with increasing Ni doping concentration, which is in line with our previously reported results.²⁸ Furthermore, the current density of all $\text{Ni}_x\text{Co}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ ($x = 0, 0.3, 1.0$) samples showed an increasing trend in OER activity with the increase of CV cycles. It is well known that the electronic structure is closely related to the OER performance. Recently, we reported that the OER performance of Ni-doped Co_3O_4 strongly correlates with both the content of Ni^{3+} and the hole states located energetically below the CBM.²⁸ However, the presented NEXAFS results of $\text{Ni}_x\text{Co}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ ($x = 0, 0.3, 1.0$) samples clearly visualize that the Ni^{3+} and hole states were rather stable upon electrochemical cycling (up to 30 cycles). Additionally, as mentioned above, the SXPS results show that the E_F of all $\text{Ni}_x\text{Co}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ shifts upwards with increasing number of CV cycles, while the upward shift of E_F indicates an increase in the distance between the O p-band center (that is the valance band maximum) and E_F , resulting in a decrease in the orbital overlap with oxygen intermediate and thus weaker bond strength, which, in turn, is unfavorable for OER performance.^{40,41} Overall, the change of surface electronic structure with OER cycling is unfavorable for the OER activity of $\text{Ni}_x\text{Co}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$. Therefore, the changes in surface properties of $\text{Ni}_x\text{Co}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ with OER cycling including change of surface composition, play a critical role in improving OER activity. To investigate the (change of) surface compositions, we calculated the atomic compositions of Ni, Co, and O ($\text{Ni}\% + \text{Co}\% + \text{O}\% = 100\%$) for the $\text{Ni}_x\text{Co}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ ($x = 0, 0.3, 1.0$) sample after each OER treatment derived from XPS, as shown in Table 2. The results demonstrate a gradual aggregation of both Co and Ni atoms towards the surface accompanied by the formation of oxygen deficiency with increasing CV cycles in all samples. It was recently reported that the introduction of oxygen deficiency in Co_3O_4 and NiCo_2O_4 could enhance the adsorption of OH^- at the active site as well as promote the deprotonation of intermediate $\text{Co}-\text{OOH}^\bullet$, resulting in an enhancement in OER activity.^{42,43} In addition, the Ni/Co ratio shows an increasing trend with increasing CV cycles, which is also responsible for the enhancement of the OER activity of $\text{Ni}_{0.3}\text{Co}_{2.7}\text{O}_4$ and NiCo_2O_4 .²⁸ Based on the obtained data, the decrease of oxygen concentration and increase of Ni/Co ratio at the samples surface during the proceeding OER analysis is considered as key parameter for the interpretation and evaluation of

the OER activity and explains the enhancement of the performance of $\text{Ni}_x\text{Co}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ ($x = 0, 0.3, 1.0$) for prolonged cycling.

Figure 6. OER performance of $\text{Ni}_x\text{Co}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ with different CV cycles. (a) NiCo_2O_4 CV polarization curves, (b) current density of $\text{Ni}_x\text{Co}_{1-x}\text{O}_4$ ($x = 0, 0.3, 1.0$) with different CV cycles at +1.8 V (vs RHE).

Table 2. XPS-derived Co, Ni and O atomic compositions ($\text{Co}\% + \text{Ni}\% + \text{O}\% = 100\%$) for $\text{Ni}_x\text{Co}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ ($x = 0, 0.3, 1.0$) with different CV cycles.

	Co_3O_4		$\text{Ni}_{0.3}\text{Co}_{2.7}\text{O}_4$				NiCo_2O_4			
	Co (at.%)	O (at.%)	Co (at.%)	Ni (at.%)	O (at.%)	Ni/Co	Co (at.%)	Ni (at.%)	O (at.%)	Ni/Co
Pristine ^a	42.9 ± 0.2	57.1 ± 0.3	38.5 ± 0.4	4.4 ± 0.3	57.1 ± 0.4	11.4 ± 0.4	28.6 ± 0.2	14.3 ± 0.3	57.1 ± 0.3	50.0 ± 0.3
0 CV ^b	42.7 ± 0.4	57.3 ± 0.2	38.6 ± 0.2	4.1 ± 0.3	57.3 ± 0.3	10.6 ± 0.3	28.7 ± 0.3	14.3 ± 0.2	57.0 ± 0.4	49.8 ± 0.3
3 CV ^b	45.2 ± 0.3	54.8 ± 0.4	40.0 ± 0.5	5.1 ± 0.4	54.9 ± 0.2	12.8 ± 0.5	27.9 ± 0.5	17.0 ± 0.4	55.1 ± 0.2	60.9 ± 0.5
10 CV ^b	46.7 ± 0.4	53.3 ± 0.3	40.6 ± 0.4	6.7 ± 0.2	52.7 ± 0.4	16.8 ± 0.4	28.3 ± 0.4	19.2 ± 0.3	52.5 ± 0.4	67.8 ± 0.4
30 CV ^b	47.3 ± 0.5	52.7 ± 0.2	42.3 ± 0.2	7.2 ± 0.3	50.5 ± 0.4	17.0 ± 0.3	29.4 ± 0.2	21.7 ± 0.2	48.9 ± 0.5	73.8 ± 0.2

^a Expected stoichiometry

^b Deduced by the variation of the area under the emission lines

Conclusion

We investigated the relationship between the surface properties, electronic structure and OER activity of epitaxial $\text{Ni}_x\text{Co}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ ($x = 0, 0.3, 1.0$) thin film model electrocatalysts prepared via pulsed laser deposition in dependence of the number of electrochemical OER cycling. Our results reveal that operating the electrocatalysts by OER cycling in alkaline media results in an enhancement of OER performance of $\text{Ni}_x\text{Co}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$. Combined quasi in-situ SXPS and NEXAS spectra reveal the energetic upward-shift of E_F in $\text{Ni}_x\text{Co}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ during the OER process, while the oxidation states of Co, Ni and the hole states created by Ni doping do not change and were found to be stable. The upward-shift of E_F in $\text{Ni}_x\text{Co}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ with increasing CV cycles is unfavorable for OER performance since it would increase the distance between the O p-band center (that is the valance band maximum) and E_F , resulting in a decrease in the orbital overlap with oxygen intermediate and thus weaker bond strength. The observed morphology change, also supported by structural characterization methods (XRD and AFM), accompanied with the emergence of an oxygen deficiency of $\text{Ni}_x\text{Co}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ was evaluated to play a key role in improving the OER performance. The presence of oxygen deficiency can facilitate OH^- adsorption at the active sites and promotes deprotonation of the intermediate, which in turn enhances OER activity. Over all, we found that the E_F shift, morphology change, the change of Ni/Co ratio and oxygen deficiency simultaneously affected the OER activity of $\text{Ni}_x\text{Co}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$, acting in balance with each other to enhance the OER performance of $\text{Ni}_x\text{Co}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$. Our study further demonstrates the importance of synchrotron-based investigations on well-defined model systems for the precise interpretation of electrochemical properties with respect to energy level engineering of the electronic structure of spinel electrocatalysts towards achieving optimized OER performance.

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